

1. EVALUATING RESIN FLOW IN NATURAL FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS USING IMAGE ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

The precise characterization of resin flow in fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) systems is critical for optimizing permeability and ensuring uniform resin distribution, particularly in bio-based natural fiber composites. Insufficient resin infiltration can result in voids, fiber debonding, and compromised mechanical properties. Predicting and optimizing resin infiltration is essential to mitigating these defects and enhancing composite performance. This study presents an image analysis algorithm developed to quantify the resin impregnation behavior in natural fiber fabric under varying fiber orientations and controlled pressure conditions. By developing an image processing pipeline consisting of smoothing, thresholding, labeling, and refining techniques, the algorithm extracts key flow metrics, including flow front position and resin-saturated area after curing. The results provide insights into flow anisotropy, confirming that resin infiltration is significantly improved in fiber direction. To validate the algorithm, a hand-annotated dataset is created, serving as ground truth for comparison and evaluation. The findings highlight the correlation between visual observations and algorithm-based measurements, reinforcing the potential of automated image analysis in enhancing process control and permeability modeling for bio-based fiber reinforced plastics.

2. INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for sustainable, high-performance materials is reshaping how fibre reinforced materials are designed and manufactured, pushing the field toward renewable, alternative composite systems with improved environmental profiles. Among the most promising candidates are natural fibre reinforced plastics, which have gained momentum as a sustainable alternative to conventional carbon or glass fibre-reinforced polymers. These materials offer a unique value proposition: they combine the advantages of renewable raw materials with the potential to lower energy consumption and reduce CO₂ emissions during production [1].

However, the advantages of bio-based fiber reinforced plastics are tempered by the complex behaviour of natural fibres during processing. Their anisotropic permeability, moisture uptake, and internal capillary structures create irregular flow paths, which hinder resin impregnation and can result in dry zones or voids [2] [3]. Uniform resin distribution is essential to ensure strong fibre-matrix bonding and consistent mechanical performance [2]. Insufficient wet-out can lead to structural defects such as delamination, dry patches, or weak interfaces, all of which degrade long-term performance.

Despite decades of development in composite process monitoring, many established methods for assessing resin flow, such as dyed resin visualization, ultrasonic scanning, or destructive sectioning, remain limited in their practical effectiveness. Ultrasonic techniques, while capable of detecting resin arrival and curing stages, often struggle with measurement accuracy due to factors like sensor placement, poor coupling, and heterogeneous material interfaces [4].

Likewise, dyed resin visualization methods, although simple and widely used, are largely qualitative, offering only surface-level insights that are often skewed by part geometry or human error. Their limitations in capturing flow anomalies in complex or thick laminates have been well-documented [5].

These limitations highlight the need for more robust, high-resolution, and automated approaches for analysing flow behaviour in natural fibre composites. Digital image analysis techniques present a compelling alternative. With the right processing pipeline, even simple post-cure images can be transformed into detailed insights about flow front location, saturation zones, and the effect of fibre orientation.

This paper introduces an image analysis-based approach to quantify resin flow in natural fibre composites. Using controlled experiments and a custom image processing pipeline, we measure flow front progression under different configurations (fibre orientation, number of layers, etc). The analysis includes validation using hand-annotated ground truth data and reveals distinct anisotropic behaviour in resin infiltration, especially along the fibre direction. These findings, by better predicting how resin will spread in various fibre architectures, allow manufacturers to optimize resin usage, improve drapability, and minimize defects such as dry spots or voids during forming and consolidation. Furthermore, digital image analysis has the potential to support automated quality assurance and process optimization in fibre reinforced plastics production.

3. RESEARCH TESTS AND EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Materials

The materials used in this study were selected for their relevance to Natural fiber reinforced plastics development. The primary reinforcement was a unidirectional flax fiber fabric (see Table 1), chosen for its mechanical properties and compatibility with epoxy systems. The matrix material was a fast-curing, solvent-free epoxy resin system (see Table 2), selected for its good flow characteristics and short cure times. Key properties of each material system are summarized in the tables below.

Table 1 Flax Fiber Reinforcement Properties (ampliTex™ 5057, Bcomp AG)

Property	Value/Description
Product name	amplitex 5057 [6]
Fiber type	flax (EU grown, France Belgium)
Yarn tex	300 tex
Fiber Density	~1450 kg/m ³
Fabric Width	1000 mm
Tensile Modulus (//)	~35 GPa
Tensile Strength (//)	~364 MPa

The ampliTex™ 5057 fabric was selected for its superior specific stiffness, improved vibration and damping effects. Its unidirectional construction with non-twisted yarns enables high stiffness and predictable mechanical behavior.

Table 2 Epoxy Resin System Properties (Epinal bto-epoxy GmbH)

Property	Value / description
Product Name	Epinal
Mixing ratio	100:15 (Resin: hardener by weight)
Final Cure Profile	80 °C for ~60 min
Pot Life	~100 minutes 23 C (100 g batch)

The resin displayed excellent flowability under heat. The short cure times and strong adhesion properties make this system particularly suited for use with natural fibre reinforcements.

3.2 Sample Fabrication

To evaluate the resin flow behaviour in natural fiber reinforced plastics, a controlled image-based analysis methodology was developed. This approach required consistent sample preparation, ensuring reproducibility across multiple orientations and process conditions. All samples were produced in-house using the materials mentioned in section 3.1. The samples for image-based flow analysis were fabricated as flat rectangular laminates with dimensions of 250 × 150 mm. Different configurations were manufactured by layering fabric to study the influence of thickness and fibre direction on resin flow. The different configurations are mentioned in table 3.

Table 3 Summary of experimental configurations for Image analysis

Experimental variable	Tested Configurations
Fibre orientation	0°, 90°, 0°+90°
Initial area of resin (cm ²)	60, 75, 90
Number of layers	1, 2, 4

A screen-printing method was employed to apply the resin system onto dry fibre layers in defined stripe patterns. This approach provided a uniform resin application with high control over distribution and volume. The fabric stacks were assembled on glass base plates, covered with a release film, followed by a breather fleece, and vacuum bagged for consolidation. The samples underwent final consolidation at 80 °C for one hour under pressure to complete the curing process and ensure structural integrity. After curing, the samples were polished to produce clear, interpretable surfaces for imaging.

3.3 Image Acquisition Methodology

All images were captured from the top surface of the laminate samples using a high-resolution digital camera with a 48 MP wide-angle sensor. Photographs were taken after the curing process, directly from above the laminate, without any sectioning. To ensure consistency across the dataset, each sample was imaged under the same lighting conditions while eliminating shadows and reducing glare. The camera was mounted on a fixed rig to maintain constant height, angle, and orientation relative to the sample surface. All photos were taken with identical framing, focus, and exposure settings, and no image filters or post-processing were applied. Particular care was taken to avoid reflections and ensure that all resin flow patterns were captured with clarity and contrast sufficient for image analysis. This standardized approach ensured reproducibility and minimized variation in image quality across all samples,

creating a reliable basis for objective flow evaluation. A schematic representation of the imaging setup is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 schematic representation of the imaging setup

3.4 Image analysis

In total 20 specimen images were captured and transferred to a main computer for further image processing. As the images were captured using a normal high-resolution camera, the image metadata does not contain information linking pixel dimensions to real-world units. That means no direct correlation between pixel size and physical length can be inferred from the image data alone. To overcome this limitation, the width of the imaging field is measured in millimeters (mm) (Fig. 2). Then the width of the digital image is measured in pixels. The area of each pixel is then calculated by dividing the width of the imaging field in mm by the width of the image in pixels, powered by two. In addition, to calculate the area of the primarily penetrated resin, the width of the laminate and the advancement-length of the primarily penetrated resin (both in mm unit) are measured (Fig.2) and provided as input to the code.

Figure 2 Areas and measurements on the preform, a. width of preform, b. width of imaging field, c. advancement-length of primarily penetrated resin, d. advance-depth of secondary penetrated resin, e. area of primarily penetrated resin, f. area of secondary penetrated resin, e+f. total area of impregnation

As the surface of the fabric has some level of texture inhomogeneity which interferes with the upcoming thresholding process, a blur filter was applied on each photo using *OpenCV* library with blur size of 60. This specific blur size was chosen as optimal by manually applying different blur sizes and inspecting the results. In the next step an *Otsu threshold* is applied on each image using the *scikit-image* library. Thresholding leads to a binary image, in which all the resin penetrated areas are represented by black (pixel value 0) and all other areas (non-impregnated preform and background) by white (pixel value 255). This process is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 process of extracting the resin area, Left: original image, Middle: blurred image, Right: binary image from thresholding

Despite the care during image acquisition and the blurring step, the possible even-minor remaining non-uniformities in lighting and laminate surface structure, can lead to incorrect detections in form of small black regions. In order to make sure all these unwanted areas are removed before proceeding, *regionprops* from the *scikit-image* library extracts all the objects in the image. By defining a threshold of specific size in accordance with the size of the image, all small objects are removed.

As the resin infusion has been carried out from both sides of the fabric (Fig. 2), the following procedures are applied on both right and left side of each image. The *count_nonzero* from *Numpy* library counts all the white pixels (non-impregnated preform and background) and subtract it from the total number of the pixels in the half image, which leads to number count of black pixels (resin impregnated parts). The total area of impregnation is then derived by multiplying the calculated number of black pixels by the former calculated pixel area. The area of the secondary penetrated resin is derived by subtracting the area of the primarily penetrated resin (formerly calculated) from the total area of impregnation (Fig. 2). The advance-depth of secondary penetrated resin is gained by dividing its area by the width of the preform. The exact same is done for the other half of each image as well.

In order to test the reliability and accuracy of the code in extracting and measuring the resin impregnated areas, 3 different images from the data set with different resin penetration patterns were selected, and the resin area was carefully manually annotated with a distinct blue color. Fig. 4 illustrates each of these images, the area detected by the code as overly (green), and the hand annotated areas (blue). Furthermore, the resin area calculated from code detection and from hand annotation are shown in table 4.

Table 4 Resin area detected by the code compared to ground truth

Area detected by the code	Ground truth	Difference %
38.78%	38.77%	-0.03%
30.13%	29.98%	-0.49%
46.31%	46.48%	0.36%

Sample No.	Original image	Segmented by image processing	Ground truth (hand annotation)
1			
2			
3			

Figure 4 resin areas detected by the code as overlay (green) and manually annotated as ground truth for comparison (blue)

4. RESULTS

4.1 Validation of Image analysis method

A visual comparison already revealed a meaningful result of segmentation of the resin impregnated areas by the developed method in Fig. 3. This was further confirmed by the results from Fig. 4, where three types of resin infusion patterns were segmented manually (as comparison ground truth) and by the developed method. A comparison shows – that regardless of the infusion patterns – the method has been able to correctly detect the resin area. Table 4 shows the resin covered area to the whole prepreg area in percent, for both code-detected and ground truth. The code returns values very close to the ground truth, with a maximum of 0.5% difference. As the visual comparison and surface area calculations showed reliable performance of the code, it was applied on the rest of the specimen images.

4.2 Results of image-based resin flow analysis

The results, illustrated in figure 5, This bar chart displays the resin penetration area in cm² (y-axis) for various initial fabric areas and fibre orientations (x-axis). The different colors represent the number of layers: 1L = 1 layer, 2L = 2 layers, 4L = 4 layers. Each combination of area (60, 75, 90 cm²) and fibre orientation (0°, 90°, 0°+90°) was tested.

Figure 5 Overview of Resin Penetration Results Across All Test Configurations

Figure 5 provides a complete overview of how resin flow behaviour changes with surface area, layer count, and fibre alignment. The resin penetration area increases with a larger initial application area. Specifically, the average penetration improves by approximately 30% when increasing the initial area from 60 cm² to 75 cm², and by an additional 13% when increased further to 90 cm². This trend results in a total increase of nearly 47% from the smallest to the largest application area. The observed effect is attributed to the greater volume of resin available for infiltration, which promotes more extensive lateral and through-thickness flow across the fabric.

Figure 6(a) quantifies the influence of fiber orientation and ply configuration on resin penetration width at a constant initial area of 75 cm². Transitioning from a 90° to a 0° fiber alignment results in an increase in penetration width of approximately 68% for the two-layer laminate and 8% for the four-layer laminate. The most significant enhancement is observed in cross-ply (0° + 90°) configurations, where penetration width increases by 85% relative to the 90° orientation (and by 11% relative to 0°) for two layers, and by 36% (and 26%) for four layers, respectively. This trend can be attributed to the anisotropic permeability inherent to fiber-reinforced textiles. When fibers are aligned in the 0° direction, resin can flow more readily along the fiber axis, resulting in a broader lateral spread compared to the transverse (90°) orientation, which restricts flow due to higher resistance across the fibers. The introduction of cross-ply arrangements (0° + 90°) creates orthogonal flow channels, facilitating multi-directional resin transport and enabling the most extensive penetration width.

Figure 6 (b) shows the effect of different numbers of layers on resin penetration at 0° fiber orientation for three initial resin application areas: 60 cm², 75 cm², and 90 cm². Across all cases, an increase in the number of layers from 1L to 4L leads to a noticeable rise in the total resin penetration area. This trend can be also explained by the higher resin demand in multi-layer systems—more layers mean a greater fiber volume to saturate, which drives the resin to infiltrate deeper and spread further. Additionally, the stacking of layers may introduce micro-channels and capillary paths between the plies that enhance resin transport, particularly in the 0° direction where fiber alignment offers lower resistance to flow. These findings underline the influence of both geometric and structural parameters in controlling resin flow behavior during impregnation.

Figure 6 (a) Effect of Fiber orientation on resin penetration area (Initial Area = 75 cm²) (b) Effect of different number of layers on Resin Penetration (0° orientation)

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of an image analysis-based method for quantifying resin flow in natural fibre reinforced plastics. The developed pipeline showed high accuracy in identifying resin-impregnated areas, with less than 0.5% deviation compared to hand-annotated ground truth.

Key findings indicate that both initial resin application area and layer count strongly influence resin penetration, with the penetration area increasing by nearly 47% as the initial area is expanded from 60 cm² to 90 cm². Additionally, fibre orientation plays a critical role: resin flows most readily along the fibre axis, and the use of cross-ply (0°+90°) configurations results in the broadest lateral resin spread, with up to 85% greater penetration width compared to unidirectional (90°) layups.

These insights emphasize the importance of geometric and structural parameters for optimizing impregnation in bio-based fibre reinforced plastic manufacturing. The results provide valuable data for process control, highlighting the potential for digital image analysis to support automated quality assurance in fiber reinforced plastics production.

Further research is recommended to investigate the detailed permeability behavior of various natural fibre architectures, especially considering a wider range of fibre orientations, stacking sequences, and multi-axial layups. Exploring the effect of fibre/matrix interface characteristics on flow behavior could further enhance the understanding and design of high-performance, sustainable prepreg systems.

6. REFERENCES

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